

Electrometric Study of Thorium(IV) Furfuryl Mercaptan Complexes

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The complexation of thorium (IV) with furfuryl mercaptan has been studied in 50% ethanolic media applying potentiometric and conductometric titration techniques. The formation curves reveal the formation of 1:3 and 1:4 complexes whose log K stab values have been determined at 25°, 35° and 45° at ionic strength of 0.5 M (NaClO₄) employing Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. The values of ΔG , ΔH and ΔS for the complexation reaction have also been reported.

MERCAPTANS act as strong complexing agents owing to the presence of -SH group. This class of compounds along with their metal complexes has great significance in biological and pharmaceutical fields. Therefore, the study on the complexation of organo-sulphur compounds with metals has drawn the attention of several research workers¹⁻⁶. There is, however, no reference in the literature regarding the study of thorium-furfuryl mercaptan system and hence the present investigation has been undertaken which describes a study of the composition of the complexes, their stability constants and determination of overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy accompanying the complexation reaction.

Experimental

Furfuryl mercaptan (referred herein as FSH) was supplied by Evan's Chemetics, Inc., New York and other chemicals were of Anal-R (BDH) grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation.

pH measurements were made on a Cambridge Bench pattern pH meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly. Conductance was measured on an electronic eye type conductometer. Universal thermostat U₃ type (German) was used to maintain the desired temperature. The experimental procedure involved a series of pH and conductometric titrations of FSH in absence and presence of Th (IV) against standard NaOH. Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method was used to calculate the stability constants of the complexes formed. The entire study was made in 50% ethanolic media and ionic strength of 0.5 M maintained by NaClO₄.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: In order to establish the stoichiometry of the complexes, potentiometric and conductometric titrations of the solutions containing different moles of FSH per mole of Th(IV) ion were performed against standard NaOH. Fig. 1

represents the pH titrations of 4.0×10^{-3} M FSH (curve a);

Fig. 1. pH titrations of
(a) 4.0×10^{-3} M FSH,
(b) 4.0×10^{-3} M FSH + 4.0×10^{-3} M Th(NO₃)₄,
(c) 4.0×10^{-3} M FSH + 2.0×10^{-3} M Th(NO₃)₄,
(d) 4.0×10^{-3} M FSH + 1.33×10^{-3} M Th(NO₃)₄,
and (e) 4.0×10^{-3} M FSH + 1.0×10^{-3} M Th(NO₃)₄
against 0.1 M NaOH.

The abscissa denotes the moles of NaOH added per mole of ligand 'm'.

The sudden rise in pH on addition of NaOH to the ligand (curve a) indicates that proton of -SH group is not titrable under the experimental conditions. The addition of an equimolar concentration of Th⁴⁺ greatly alters the shape of the free ligand titration curve indicating the complex formation which results in lowering of buffer region due to the proton displacement.

Since the extent of the proton displacement depends on the relative affinities of the ligand for H^+ and metal ions, it is obvious from the curve that the affinity for Th^{4+} is great enough to compete with the relatively high concentration of hydrogen ions. The inflection in the vicinity of $m = 4$ indicates that the reaction (1) is followed by further reactions involving three more hydroxyl ions. The appearance of precipitate suggests the disproportionation of $Th(FS)^{3+}$ accompanying the formation of metal hydroxide as shown below

When metal and ligand are mixed in the ratio of 1 : 2, the inflection is obtained at $m = 2$ with the precipitation of metal hydroxide which can be explained as

followed by

The inflections at $m \approx 1.33$ and 1.0 when the ratio of metal to ligand is 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 respectively confirm the formation of $Th(FS)_4$ as the highest complex in accordance with the following equations :

followed by

and

Conductometric titrations of FSH in absence and presence of Th^{4+} mixed in different ratios against 0.1 M NaOH (Fig. 2) yield the breaks corresponding to the results obtained from pH titrations.

The stability constants of 1 : 3 and 1 : 4 complexes have been determined at 25°, 35° and 45° by Bjerrum's method⁷ as extended by Calvin and Melchior⁸ and the mean values of $\log K_3$ and $\log K_4$ are 8.94 and 8.54 respectively.

Thermodynamic Functions : The values of change in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) for the complexation reaction have been determined at 35° applying the standard equations⁹.

The value of ΔG obtained from the expression

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln \beta_4 \text{ is } -24.68 \text{ Kcal/mole.}$$

Fig. 2. Conductometric titrations of (a) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ FSH, (b) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ FSH + $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$, (c) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ FSH + $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$, (d) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ FSH + $1.33 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$, and (e) $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ FSH + $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Th(NO_3)_4$ against 0.1 M NaOH.

where β_4 , the overall stability constant, is evaluated from the relation $\log \beta_4 = \log K_3 + \log K_4$.¹⁰

The value of ΔH is determined from the isobar

$$\frac{d \ln \beta_4}{dT} = \frac{\Delta H}{RT^2}$$

which can be written as

$$\frac{d(\log \beta_4)}{d(1/T)} = \frac{\Delta H}{4.57}$$

The values of $\log \beta_4$ were plotted as a function of $1/T$ and the gradient of the tangent at the point corresponding to 35° was equated to $-\Delta H/4.57$ and thus ΔH was found to be 2.38 Kcal/mole.

The value of ΔS was then evaluated from the relation

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T}$$

and found to be 87.86 cal/mole/degree.

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